

PREPARATION OF H-FORM OF ZSM-5 ZEOLITE

Seyidova Fidan Famil,

Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University

Ayrarova Tamara İbrahim

Phd., Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University

Abstract

The article presents the results of studies conducted to increase the activity of the zeolite ZSM-5 catalyst for the alkylation of benzene with olefins. ZSM-5 was converted to H-form to obtain the active form of zeolite.

Keywords: ZSM-5 zeolite, alkylation process, ion exchange method, activation

INTRODUCTION: The earliest alkylation/trans-alkylation technologies used strong mineral or Lewis acids (e.g., HF, H₂SO₄, AlCl₃) as catalysts. These acids are toxic, dangerous to handle and transport, corrosive to equipment and poorly recovered, the occurrence of secondary reactions reduces the selectivity of the main reaction, and also requires the cost of purification of primary alkylbenzenes and recovery of secondary products, large amounts of waste water, including acids is formed, which requires the costs of their cleaning. Processes using Lewis acids as catalysts also have a number of disadvantages: rapid deactivation of the catalyst, complexity of regeneration, introduction of the active component and accumulation of acid sludge during the disposal of the catalyst. A promising solution to existing technological problems and existing shortcomings is the use of zeolite-containing catalysts for the alkylation / transalkylation processes of aromatic hydrocarbons. transition to heterogens. The use of such catalysts simplifies the technology of the process (catalyst separation and regeneration); reduction of costs for preparation of raw materials, washing of the reaction mass and neutralization of acidic wastewater; equipment corrosion is reduced; facilitates the organization of continuous processes [1].

In the literature, the catalyst was obtained in several steps, first by mixing the highly dispersed zeolite HZSM-5 with pseudobentonite 70/30%. Then the resulting mass is mixed to a homogeneous consistency and turned into pellets by extrusion and dried at room temperature at 120-150°C for 3 hours and then subjected to heat treatment for 4 hours at 650 °C in air for 3 hours. In a series of experiments, the catalyst was subjected to curing at 550°C for 1 hour and 500°C for 3 hours [2].

EXPERIMENTAL PART: Experimental studies of the reaction of alkylation of benzene with ethylene were carried out in a laboratory reactor with a fixed bed of ZSM-5 catalyst containing granular zeolite. During the experiments, the reaction temperature (T=380–440°C), reactor pressure (P=21–31 at), volume rates of benzene (wb=10–20 h⁻¹) and ethylene (wb=360–720 h⁻¹) were varied.) or their general analogue is the contact time of the reaction mixture with the catalyst. Under such experimental conditions, the molar ratio of ethylene to benzene (E : B) varied from 1:5 to 1:9, and the contact time varied from 7 to 14 s [3].

Yttrium was obtained by impregnating H-form of zeolite with yttrium nitrate solution at 80°C for 6 hours. Samples were dried in air for 16 hours and then calcined in oven at 110°C for 4 hours. Experiments were

conducted in a plug reactor at atmospheric pressure in a fixed bed flow-type device with a 4 cm³ catalyst layer (grain size 0.25-0.5 mm) in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 550°C for 4 hours. 300-500°C range, feed space speed 2 hours and benzene: ethanol molar ratio: H₂=2:1:1. The duration of the experiment is 30 minutes. Analysis of reaction products is carried out using gas chromatography [6].

In another study, we used ZSM-5 zeolite with a modulus of about 30.0 in the form of Na synthesized with hexamethylenediamine (NH₂(CH₂)₆NH₂) for the synthesis of granular catalysts. prepared by ion exchange, the ratio of NH₄⁺ cations in the solution and Na⁺ cations in the zeolite is G = 1.5 g- eq/g-eq, pH = 5.5–7.0, and the duration is 1 hour, the number of exchanges is 3. After exchange, the solid phase is washed with distilled water, dried and heat treated in air at a temperature of 540-650°C. 4-6 hours until smooth. The mass was extruded into pellets, dried and calcined in air at 640-650°C for 4-6 hours [5].

RESULT: The conversion of HZSM-5 type zeolite to NH₄ form by ion exchange was used. The H form of zeolite was obtained as a result of thermal decomposition of the NH₄ form.

Literature

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